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THE ANALYSIS OF ROUTE MAPPING WITHIN MODIBBO ADAMA UNIVERSITY, YOLA

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Abstract

This study was carried out to map and analyse the road network of Modibbo Adama University Yola. The network consists of series of interconnected roads, this is to say more than one road provides access to a particular feature. This research provides a scientific solution for identifying the shortest route leading to any feature among the numerous routes leading to the same feature. In doing this, ground surveying method using handheld GPS was adopted for data capturing coordinate of road junction as node, shapefiles for roads and buildings within study area created and digitized, which was integrated to GIS for analysis, based on the network dataset created for the ArcGIS network analyst for shortest route identification. The results obtained were: Map showing all routes paving entrance to the campus; sample of comparison between the shortest route and the alternative route from hostel to clinic, hostel to security office and Engineering complex to campus gate. In conclusion, the use of GIS in route analysis for shortest route identification for emergency purpose like accident and health issue saves time and socioeconomic activities.

Keywords: Route Mapping, Road Network, GPS, GIS

Introduction

Road network is a several interconnected lines and points representing a system of road or street in a given area. There is need to identify the shortest route between any two locations in the network. This is a pressing need in our society today because it has formed a basis for route analysis, for instance, determining the shortest route to any location or between any two features is of paramount importance to individuals, visitors, investors, security agencies and the entire public at large. This can easily be achieved through route studies. Route analysis determines the fastest route to access any location out of the numerous routes leading to the same location thereby reducing travel time, determines the best route to tackle cases of emergencies in order to save lives, time, resources, energy, aid effective planning and the ease of accessing facilities in the location. Furthermore, the security defects of any area can be curbed by proper route analysis. With the present public need for transportation regeneration, the concept of route analysis must be considered so as to better develop our infrastructures and also enhancing security in the society by monitoring the routes paving entrance to the society, the concept of route analysis must be considered if this entire valuable must be achieved.

In the present study, the road network in Modibbo Adama University Yola has been selected for analysis, which involves finding the shortest route linking any two locations in the campus. i.e. the shortest route connecting the campus

gate to any features (senate building, schools, hostels, clinic, security office, bus stop, E-library) in the campus and also telling the conditions of these roads. Over the years, there has been an increasing interest in problem of route analysis in the campus because only route analysis can show where a road is and where it leads to, thereby determining the shortest route linking any two locations in the campus out of the numerous routes connecting them in the road network. In order to answer questions often asked by visitors, individuals, staffs, investors and the whole campus community at large, i.e., questions like, where is the route leading to senate building, Lecture Theatres (LTs), Clinic, among others. More so, it is believed that identifying the shortest route between any two locations in any road network saves time, cost, energy and also solve problems of insurgence, disaster, emergencies (health, delivery from accident spot, fire outbreak among others).

Study Area

Modibbo Adama University Yola campus is located at Sangere in Girei Local Government Area, of Adamawa State, along Jimeta- Mubi road, in the North- Eastern part of Nigeria. The study area lies between latitude $9^{\circ} 20' 30''N$ to $9^{\circ} 21' 05''N$ and longitude $12^{\circ}29' 48''E$ to $12^{\circ} 30' 25''E$.

Figure 1: Map of Adamawa Showing Girei Local Government
 (Source: Ministry of Land and Survey, Yola, Adamawa State)

Figure 2: Map of Girei Showing the Study Area
 (Source: Ministry of Land and Survey, Yola, Adamawa State)

Material and Method

Methodology

This involves the procedure that was used to accomplish the aim and objectives of the project. This includes the various techniques that were adopted and used to obtain the desired result.

Figure 3: Model of Work Flow
 (Source: Modified from Aman Arora, 2012)

Material/Equipment Used

The accompanying materials and equipment used were;

Hardware

1. Handheld GPS

Software

1. Arc GIS 10.1

Data Required

- ✓ Ground truth data
- ✓ Satellite image

Data Manipulation and Analysis

Georeferencing

Georeferencing was carried out by adhering to all necessary steps before digitizing.

Digitizing

Before digitizing was carried out, shapefile for roads and buildings within Modibbo Adama University was created. After the shapefiles have been created, digitizing was carried out.

Adding field for distance and travel time

A field name meters was added to the characteristics table for simplicity ascertaining the travel time by utilizing the field mini-computer, after which two new fields were added to the quality and was named “FT_minute (Fromto)” and “TF_minute (Tofrom)” on the grounds that, that is the dialect saw by the system information set utilized for most limited course distinguishing proof. This was really done to know the measure of time in minutes that will take to head out a specific polyline To and Fro at a certain rate.

Table 1 Attribute table for calculated FT and TF

FID	Shape *	Id	Road_Name	FT_Meters	TF_Meters	FT_Minutes	TF_Minutes	Conditn_ID
0	Polyline	0	Yola - Mubi Road	852.7013	852.7013	0.7106	0.7106	2
1	Polyline	0	Campus Gate Road	414.4973	414.4973	0.3454	0.3454	1
2	Polyline	0	Round about to Right- Primary School	48.5228	48.5228	0.0404	0.0404	1
3	Polyline	0	Primary School Road	112.7155	112.7155	0.0939	0.0939	1
4	Polyline	0	PDP/GS Road	101.851	101.851	0.0849	0.0849	1
5	Polyline	0	Security Unit Road	108.8164	108.8164	0.0907	0.0907	1
6	Polyline	0	Admin/Senate Building Road	518.4028	518.4028	0.432	0.432	1
7	Polyline	0	School of Agric Road	266.6234	266.6234	0.2222	0.2222	1
8	Polyline	0	SMIT/LT 5 Road	403.8979	403.8979	0.3366	0.3366	1
9	Polyline	0	New Surveying/Engineering Road	550.8259	550.8259	0.459	0.459	1
10	Polyline	0	Store/CMIT Road	212.7491	212.7491	0.1773	0.1773	1
11	Polyline	0	VC Former House Road	67.5109	67.5109	0.0563	0.0563	1
12	Polyline	0	Commercial /Quaters Road	90.4877	90.4877	0.0754	0.0754	1
13	Polyline	0	Quaters Road/Guest House Road	501.0407	501.0407	0.4175	0.4175	1
14	Polyline	0	GS Road	56.4959	56.4959	0.0471	0.0471	3
15	Polyline	0	SPG Road	140.8165	140.8165	0.1173	0.1173	3
16	Polyline	0	Quaters Road 1	65.3244	65.3244	0.0544	0.0544	3
17	Polyline	0	Quaters Road 2	99.8393	99.8393	0.0832	0.0832	3
18	Polyline	0	Basket Ball Road	60.5805	60.5805	0.0505	0.0505	3
19	Polyline	0	Lab. Tech. Road	29.5399	29.5399	0.0246	0.0246	3
20	Polyline	0	Quaters/Lab. Tech Road	98.8117	98.8117	0.0823	0.0823	3
21	Polyline	0	Primary School /Saff Quaters Road	94.6438	94.6438	0.0789	0.0789	3
22	Polyline	0	Basket ball /SIWES Road	151.6066	151.6066	0.1263	0.1263	3
23	Polyline	0	Clinic/Mosque Road	154.5106	154.5106	0.1288	0.1288	1
24	Polyline	0	Quaters/Clinic Road	53.3292	53.3292	0.0444	0.0444	1
25	Polyline	0	Quaters Road 4	134.1135	134.1135	0.1118	0.1118	3
26	Polyline	0	Quaters Road 3	153.1486	153.1486	0.1276	0.1276	3
27	Polyline	0	Adetona/Quater Road	125.9767	125.9767	0.105	0.105	1
28	Polyline	0	Nana Asmau Road/Abuja Hostel Road	590.1544	590.1544	0.4918	0.4918	1
29	Polyline	0	Quaters Road 5	65.9244	65.9244	0.0549	0.0549	2
30	Polyline	0	Quaters Road 6	144.5696	144.5696	0.1205	0.1205	2
31	Polyline	0	Old TE/Old Library Road	431.1002	431.1002	0.3593	0.3593	2
32	Polyline	0	Kabiru Umah Hostel Road	258.0718	258.0718	0.2151	0.2151	2

OID	Conditn_ID	Condition
0	1	Good
1	2	Fair
2	3	Bad

Creating a network dataset

Network dataset was modelled, created based on road shapefile and can also be created based on road feature class.

Route analysis and best route identification

The best route was chosen owing to some considerations like shortest route from an origin to the destination, road conditions and the parameters like distance and time set for analysis in the network dataset.

Adding stops

The next step taking was adding of stops, this is to depict where the analysis starts alongside where it stops, the analysis starts from the origin and ends at the destination, hence stops were used to define that. The network analyst automated to calculate the optimum route.

Setting up parameters for the Analysis

It is a methodology of tagging the course that will be ascertained and focused around travel time (minutes), separation (meter) and U- turns are permitted all over the place.

Computing the best route

Table 2: sample of comparison between the best routes and alternative routes

Origin-Destination	Shortest Route Distance (m)	Alternative Route Distance (m)	Difference Between Distances (m)	Travel Time for shortest Route (min)	Travel Time for Alternative Route (min)	Difference Between Travel Time (min)
Kibiru Umar Hostel to Clinic	1217.3	1218.4	1.1	1.014	1.015	0.001
Kibiru Umar Hostel to Security Office	1154.8	1292.5	137.7	0.962	1.077	0.115
Engineering Complex to Campus Gate	1973.7	2111.3	137.6	1.645	1.759	0.114
Summary	The alternative route is longer than the shortest route; hence, has a longer travel time					

Results and Discussions

The results obtained in this study are centered on a road network map. Some of the results obtained are

- ✓ Map Showing all routes paving entrance to the campus
- ✓ A sample of comparison between the shortest route and the alternative route from hostel to clinic, hostel to security office, and Engineering complex to campus gate

Figure 4: Road network and route paving entrance to the campus

Figure 7: shortest route from Engineering complex to main campus gate

Figure 8: alternative route from Engineering complex to campus gate

The maps produced some samples of shortest routes identification as analysed. Figure 4 is a digital map of Modibbo Adama University is a map vectored map incorporated with the ArcGIS network analyst coupled with the network dataset of the campus, which makes it capable of calculating the shortest route connecting any two locations in the campus. This map has different layers of the road network. The map integrated the entire road within the campus together. The map also contains in its layer the existing structures, new structures. For the purpose of analysis, this map proffers opportunity to selected

features that will participate in the analysis. On the map showing the road network of the campus, all features in the campus is shown and the route interconnecting them, knowing where a route is located is one thing and knowing where the route leads to is another thing, this map show the features from where a route generate and where it leads to in a general overview, should in case one is visiting the campus for the first time, it gives an insight of the road network.

Figure 5 is a sample of: shortest route analysis from Kabiru Umar hostel to security office, while Figure 7 is shortest route from Engineering complex to campus gate. The shortest route linking any two locations within the campus can be obtained from the digital map produced. In determining the shortest route, our major concern is distance and time, as the roads are in good condition and tarred. this is because in emergency situations like accidents, fire disaster and health challenges one (1) second can save a life and also travelling through the best route has a way of saving energy and resources.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The research on the integration of ground data in collaboration with the satellite image of the Modibbo University into ArcGIS environment, thereby showing that the roads are well connected with high degree of interconnectivity. Furthermore, the accuracy of the shortest route analysis is more accurate in ArcGIS environment, thereby highlighting application of GIS in route analysis for the determination of shortest route since mere eyes of analysing the shortest route is not scientific and does not lead to accurate results. The study recommends the use of Geographical Information System in routes analysis for shortest route identification for road networks.

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